

Table 1. Mass balance of 300 mg incorporated KNO₃-N and urea N in flooded soil at grain maturity stage, 1986.

¹⁵ N fraction	¹⁵ N recovery (%)		Difference between treatments ^a (mg/pot)
	Planted	Un-planted	
KNO ₃			
Soil	3.5	3.7	
Plant	1.2	–	
Recovered	4.6	3.7	
Unaccounted for	95.4	96.3	2.8 ^{ns}
Urea			
Soil	43.9	78.1	
Plant	43.6	–	
Recovered	87.5	78.1	
Unaccounted for	12.5	21.9	28.3*

^a* = significant at 5%, ns = not significant by T-test.

Table 2. Mass balance of 600 mg banded urea N in flooded soil at 3 growth stages, 1987.

¹⁵ N fraction	¹⁵ N recovery (%)		Difference between treatments ^a (mg/pot)
	Planted	Un-planted	
<i>Six-leaf stage</i>			
Soil	81.6	91.5	
Plant	13.7	–	
Recovered	95.3	91.5	
Unaccounted for	4.7	8.5	23.0 ^{ns}
<i>Panicle initiation stage</i>			
Soil	56.6	74.6	
Plant	24.6	–	
Recovered	81.2	74.6	
Unaccounted for	18.8	25.4	39.5 ^{ns}
<i>Grain maturity stage</i>			
Soil	57.9	59.0	
Plant	23.4	–	
Recovered	81.3	59.0	
Unaccounted for	18.7	41.0	134.0**

^a** = significant at 1%, ns = not significant by T-test.

samples at 300 mg N/pot in 1986. In 1987, only ¹⁵N-labeled urea solution was used at 600 mg N/pot. Band application was simulated by applying solution at a depth of 5 cm in a circle 8 cm in diameter.

Rice plants had no significant effect on losses of KNO₃-N (Table 1). Loss was more than 95% in both planted and unplanted pots, probably through denitrification. With urea (Table 1, 2), N losses were significantly higher from unplanted pots in both years.

The difference between unplanted and planted treatments in urea N unaccounted for was greater in the banded application in 1987 (22.3%) than in incorporated urea in 1986 (9.4%). Since twice as much urea was band applied, we cannot conclude whether its losses were higher than those with

incorporation.

Growing rice plants effectively reduced the urea N losses from flooded soil, even though plant roots sometimes stimulated denitrification. Urea N losses were probably due to ammonia volatilization, but denitrification cannot be ruled out. □

Organic and inorganic N effect on rice

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We studied the integrated effects of dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata*, azolla *Azolla pinnata*, and N, P, and K fertilizers during winter 1987 at TRRI, in medium-duration IR20. The soil was clayey loam with available status of 222 kg N, 29.9 kg P, and 12.45 kg K/ha. pH was 7.3.

One week before transplanting rice, 60-d-old dhaincha (3.2% N, 0.31% P,

and 1.1% K on dry weight basis) was cut and incorporated at 12.5 t/ha. One week after transplanting, azolla at 1 t/ha on fresh weight basis (3.07% N, 0.07% P, and 0.15% K on dry weight basis) was applied and allowed to multiply and disintegrate by itself.

Azolla improved grain yield when applied with inorganic N or with dhaincha (see table).

Dhaincha at 12.5 t/ha gave significantly better grain yield than 40 kg N. Dhaincha applied with 40 kg N was even better than 80 kg N.

The combined application of dhaincha and azolla was equal to 80 kg N/ha. □

Effects of dhaincha and azolla on grain yield of IR20. Aduthurai, India, 1987 winter.

Treatment	Mean plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
1. Control	73.3	6.8	2.7
2. 0 kg N + 8.7 kg P + 16.6 kg K/ha	74.4	7.0	2.9
3. 40 kg N + 8.7 kg P + 16.6 kg K/ha	73.7	7.6	3.2
4. Azolla + treatment 2	71.2	6.2	2.9
5. Azolla + treatment 3	75.6	7.5	3.7
6. Dhaincha + treatment 2	82.7	8.5	4.0
7. Dhaincha + treatment 3	84.5	9.9	4.6
8. Dhaincha + azolla + treatment 2	81.9	9.0	4.4
9. 80 kg N + 17.4 kg P + 33.2 kg K/ha	77.1	8.4	4.1
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.3	0.9	0.4

Effect of plant spacing on N release of sulfur-coated urea (SCU) in wetland rice

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SCU's controlled release rate helps reduce N losses in wetland soil, thereby producing higher yields than other urea materials. As the sulfur coating

decomposes, N is released. This process is affected by temperature, soil microbial activity, soil water, method of application, and coating characteristics.

To examine an additional factor, we studied the effect of plant spacing on N release patterns of SCU in wetland rice.

We used 2 spacings, 15 × 20 cm and 20 × 10 cm, in a sandy loam soil (Typic Ustochrept). The soil had pH 8.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, 0.23% organic C, 0.04% total N, and 4 meq cation exchange

Changes in urea N remaining at deep placement sites after application of SCU in a wetland soil. Ludhiana, India, 1988.

capacity/100 g. A nylon screen bag with 460 mg N as SCU (38.6% N) was placed between 2 layers of wet soil freshly collected from the lower layer of 3- × 5-cm or six 20- × 10 cm rice hills 5 d after transplanting of 45-d-old seedlings of cultivar PR106. The plots received a basal dose of 26 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design.

Five nylon bags from each treatment were chosen at random and SCU granules were digested, then analyzed for urea N at 6, 10, 25, 45, and 60 d after placement. The remaining wet soil mass was extracted with 2 M KCl-PMA solution, and the extract was also analyzed for urea N.

Results showed that SCU granules released urea N at a fairly controlled rate up to 60 d after placement. Spacing significantly affected the amounts of SCU N recovered. SCU N disappeared faster in the closer plant spacing (see figure). Closer plant spacing had more impact after 30 d of SCU placement, coinciding with active proliferation of rice roots. Furthermore, dissolution rate of SCU was about 9 and 19% higher than its empirical 7-d dissolution rate of 21% with 15- × 20-cm and 20- × 10-cm spacings, respectively. □

Effect of azolla and other fertilizers on rice yields

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We evaluated azolla as an organic manure, varying application rate and percentage of substitution for chemical fertilizer at RARS Pattambi during rabi seasons (Sep-Jan) of 1980 and 1981.

In the split-plot experiment, azolla at 5.0, 7.5, and 10.0 t/ha was compared with cattle manure and green leaves

(*Gliricidia maculata*) at 5 t/ha. Subplot treatment was the percentage of fertilizer dose (90:45:45 kg NPK/ha) applied. The sandy loam soil contained 0.02% available N, 9.7 kg available P, and 184.4 kg K with a pH of 5.5. On dry weight basis, cattle manure has 9.4% dry matter, 1.52% N, 0.4% P, and 21.1% K; for gliricidia, the values are 21.1, 2.6, 0.5, and 1.4%.

Substituting 5 t azolla/ha for cattle manure saved 25% of the fertilizer dose (see table). Azolla at 7.5 t/ha with full dose of fertilizer recorded the highest grain and straw yields. Applying more than 7.5 t azolla/ha was not beneficial. □

Effect of organic manures and fertilizer levels on grain yield of rice. Pattambi, India, 1980 and 1981 rabi (Sep-Jan).

Organic manure	Rate (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) with given fertilizer dose ^a				
		0	25%	50%	75%	100%
Control	0	1.8	2.3	2.7	3.1	3.6
Cattle manure	5.0	2.4	2.7	3.1	3.1	3.6
Green leaves	5.0	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.8
Azolla	5.0	2.1	2.7	2.8	3.4	3.7
Azolla	7.5	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.7	4.2
Azolla	10.0	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.2	3.7
<i>F</i> test ^b		*				
LSD (0.05)		0.27 ^c	0.29 ^d			

^aFertilizer dose: 90-45-45 kg NPK/ha. ^bSignificant at 0.05 level. ^cFor comparing 2 fertilizer levels at the same level of organic manure. ^dFor comparing 2 organic manures at the same or different levels of fertilizer.

Effects of seedling age and zinc application on yield of rice

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We evaluated the impact of seedling age and Zn application on rice in wet season, using three seedling ages as main plots, five rates of Zn applied through soil and one foliar spray as subplots, with three replications (see table). Seedlings (30, 40, and 50 d old) of variety Pant Dhan 4 were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing. Soil was Beni silty clay loam, fine silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic

Hapludoll with pH 7.6, CEC 20 meq/100 g, 1.0% organic C, 20 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 0.8 ppm Zn.

Grain yield declined significantly with increasing seedling age (see table). Panicles/m² and filled grains/panicle were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones. Filled grain percentage and 1,000-grain weight were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones.

Application of 8 ppm Zn gave significantly higher yield than other Zn treatments; 4 ppm Zn was significantly superior to Zn spray, 1 ppm Zn, and the control. Panicles/m², filled grains/panicle, and filled grains percentage were significantly higher with 8 ppm Zn than with all other